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Effect of grain and forage legumes on the yield of rice- and potato-based cropping systems in Nepal

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A field experiment was set up at Hattiban Research Station, Khumaltar, in Kathmandu Valley in July 1994 to determine the effect of various legumes on the yield of rice- and potato-based cropping systems. Rice was grown on all plots using only half the recommended fertilizer rate (30-13.2-24.9 kg NPK ha⁻¹) to create uniform soil fertility over the site. Immediately after the rice harvest in October, cropping patterns (see table) were established in four replications with plots measuring 3 × 5 m in a randomized block design. Two of the treatments simulated farmers' irrigated cropping patterns: fallow-potato-rice and wheat-rice.

All legumes were sown using minimum tillage between rows of rice stubble; for the fallow treatment, the field was left uncultivated. In February 1995, potato was planted following treatments 1 to 4 after incorporation of leguminous vegetative material as green manure. In May 1995, potato, wheat, and the remaining legume

crops were harvested and both yield and dry matter were determined. Grain legume crop residues and white clover pasture were then incorporated into the soil before direct-seeding rice in all treatments. The rice crop was harvested in October 1995 and the same treatments were repeated during the 1995-96 season. Crop cultivars used were rice (Khumal 4), wheat (Sonaliika), potato (Kufri jyoti), pea (local), lupin (1994 Swiss-*L. alba*, 1995 Merrit-*L. angustifolius*), faba bean (local), and white clover (Huia).

The experimental field was irrigated as required; three times each during the 7-mo legume period, the potato season, and the rice crop. No fertilizer or farmyard manure was used on any treatment.

Before the 1995 and 1996 rice crop, composite soil samples at two depths (0-15 and 15-30 cm) were taken from all treatments for analysis of pH, organic matter, total N (Kjeldahl), available P (Olsen), and exchangeable K.

The most effective legume that increased rice production was white clover (see table). In both years, significant increases in rice total dry matter (TDM) occurred when compared with either of the two farmer practices (an average of 158% in 1995 and 61% in 1996).

Growing of grain legumes during winter and spring also resulted in increased rice production (see table). In 1994-95, while faba bean grew normally, producing a reasonable yield and residual dry matter, lupin failed to nodulate and had poor growth. With inoculation the next year, however, lupin grew very well, producing yields similar to those of faba bean. This was reflected in the subsequent rice crop. There was a strong correlation between the increase in rice TDM (compared with the farmer practice) and the amount of legume residual dry matter (RDM) incorporated prior to planting over both years (see figure). For every 5 t RDM ha⁻¹ incorporated, rice biomass increased by 3 t ha⁻¹.

Grain and forage legume production (t ha⁻¹) in rice- and potato-based cropping patterns, Kathmandu Valley, Nepal.

Cropping pattern and time of planting			1994-95				1995-96				
			Legume TDM ^a (Feb) ^b	Crop yield (May)	Legume RDM ^c (May)	Rice TDM (Oct)	Legume TDM (Feb)	Crop yield (May)	Legume RDM (May)	Rice yield (Oct)	Rice TDM (Oct)
Fallow- (farmer's practice)	potato-	rice	-	9.4	-	4.9	-	6.8	-	4.1	9.6
Pea-	potato-	rice	0.2	11.2	-	6.0	4.2	13.2	-	5.2	12.0
Lupin-	potato-	rice	0.4	10.0	-	5.8	3.6	11.7	-	4.7	11.1
Faba-	potato-	rice	0.3	12.0	-	4.7	2.8	12.1	-	4.4	10.0
Wheat- (farmer's practice)		rice	-	3.3	-	5.3	-	1.4	-	4.3	10.4
Lupin-		rice	-	0.5	0.9	6.0	-	2.8	6.3	5.6	13.4
Faba-		rice	-	1.4	2.1	7.3	-	2.5	4.9	5.6	12.8
White clover-	rice	-	-	13.2	13.1	-	-	8.9	6.5	16.2	-
				(potato)				(potato)			
F test				ns		**		**		**	**
LSD (0.05)				-		2.05		1.65		0.82	2.08

^aTDM = total dry matter. ^bTime of harvest. ^cRDM = residual dry matter after grain harvest. ^dns = not significant.

The spring potato crop also responded positively to the application of green manure; on average, 17% in 1995 and 81% in 1996 (see table). Vegetative production of the pea, lupin, and faba bean crops was much greater in 1996 than in 1995, possibly because of a combination of seasonal effects and improved management during the second year (inoculation

of the lupin crop and more timely irrigations). Although significant responses to green manure incorporation were measured in both the rice and potato crops, analysis of soil samples taken before the rice crop was planted showed no significant change in any of the soil parameters measured.

Performance of indica/japonica derivatives in wet and boro season in West Bengal, India

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Yield and profitability of rice grown in boro season (November-May) in eastern India and Bangladesh could be increased if indica varieties with cold tolerance during the seedling and early vegetative stages are available. Furthermore, farmers prefer varieties that can be grown successfully in both the boro and wet season (June-October). IR36 is now widely used by farmers in West Bengal, India, but its performance is not satisfactory. Some hybrids have shown good performance in the boro season, but their high seed cost is a setback.

Three tolerant indica-type advanced lines developed from indica/japonica or indica/tropical japonica crosses (I/J) with putatively moderate cold tolerance at the seedling stage—(1) IR57098-2B-10-2 (IR31868-64-2-3-3-3/Leng Kwang), (2) IR58565-12-2-2 (Bg94/SR4095-19-2-3-5-4), and (3) IR61608-3B-20-2-2-1 (IR32429-47-3-2-2/Dobong byeo/Moroberakan) were tested for yield along with IR36 and hybrid CNHR3. Entries were grown in Anandapur and Midnapore, West Bengal, in the 1996-97 boro season and 1997 wet season to determine whether I/J derivatives were better than IR36 and CNHR3 for cultivation in both seasons. In the wet season,

entries were tested under both irrigated transplanted conditions and rainfed direct-seeded conditions with 60-13.2-24.9 kg NPK ha⁻¹. Trials were conducted in a randomized complete block design with four replications. The net plot size harvested for yield estimation was 10 m² for the seeded trial. In the boro season, fertilizer level was 100-22-41.5 kg NPK ha⁻¹ with a harvested net plot size of 11.25 m². The experimental design was the same as in the

wet season. All experimental fields were hand-weeded. Insecticides were not applied because there was no visible pest damage.

The table summarizes data on days to flowering and yield obtained from the experiments. The direct-seeded rainfed experiment was affected by drought during the vegetative stage. As a result, flowering was delayed and yields were low—about one-third less than those of the irrigated

Days to flowering and mean grain yield of three indica/japonica derivatives, indica hybrid CNHR3, and IR36 tested in wet and boro seasons in Anandapur, West Bengal, India.

Genotype	Wet season				Boro season		Mean (t ha ⁻¹)
	Direct-seeded and rainfed		Transplanted and irrigated		Transplanted		
	Days to flowering	Yield ^a (t ha ⁻¹)	Days to flowering	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Days to flowering	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
IR57098-2B-10-2	80	3.2 b	78	4.0 d	125	6.2 c	4.5
IR58565-12-2-2	84	3.8 a	77	5.9 a	124	9.2 a	6.3
IR61608-3B-20-2-2-1	82	3.2 b	77	5.2 b	126	8.0 ab	5.5
CNHR3	74	2.6 c	78	4.7 c	123	9.2 a	5.5
IR36	77	2.1 d	80	4.0 d	130	7.0 bc	4.4
Mean	79	3.0	78	4.7	126	7.0	
CV(%)		7.7		7.3		12.8	

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

*Deceased